

Local Government in Albania

Responses to Urban-Rural Challenges

edited by

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November 2021

The Country Report on Local Government in Albania is a product of the LoGov-project: “Local Government and the Changing Urban-Rural Interplay”.

The H2020-MSCA-RISE-2018 project aims to provide solutions for local governments that address the fundamental challenges resulting from urbanisation. To address these complex issues, 18 partners from 17 countries and six continents share their expertise and knowledge in the realms of public law, political science, and public administration. LoGov identifies, evaluates, compares, and shares innovative practices that cope with the impact of changing urban-rural relations in major local government areas (WP 1-5).

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This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 823961.

Contents

1. The System of Local Government in Albania	1
2.1. Local Responsibilities and Public Services in Albania: An Introduction	6
2.2. <i>Decentralized Early Childhood Education</i>	9
3.1. Local Financial Arrangements in Albania: An Introduction.....	16
3.2. <i>The Allocation of the General-Purpose Unconditional Grant and Fiscal Equalization</i>	19
4.1. The Structure of Local Government in Albania: An Introduction	26
4.2. <i>The Territorial and Administrative Reform</i>	29
5.1. Intergovernmental Relations of Local Governments in Albania: An Introduction.....	36
5.2. <i>Intergovernmental Dialogue through a Formal Two-Level Executive Mechanism of Policy Consultation and Coordination: CLFCC</i>	38
6.1. People’s Participation in Local Decision-Making in Albania: An Introduction	44
6.2. <i>Atelier Kanina - 100 Albanian Villages: Civic Engagement Towards Urban-Rural Linkages</i>	48

People's Participation in Local Decision-Making

6.1. People's Participation in Local Decision-Making in Albania: An Introduction

Elton Stafa, *NALAS – Network of Associations of Local Authorities of South-East Europe*

While an independent country since 1912, nearly half a century (1944-1990) of dictatorship and highly centralized government left a legacy of repressive and non-democratic institutions in Albania, with major implications on citizens' trust in institutions and participation in decision-making. In recent years, however, the general framework for people's participation in policy-making became more open to the general public, via an improved legal framework, the creation of new institutions and platforms which facilitate public participation in policy-making. In some cases, citizens' participation in decision-making became formally obligatory.

The 1998 Constitution guarantees the right of all citizens to access to information on all national and local government activities and follow up meetings of collectively elected organs (Article 24); the right to submit requests, complaints and observations to public institutions, and the latter are obliged to respond within timelines and conditions set by law (Article 48). From this perspective, there are no constitutional provisions requiring all public authorities, including therefore local governments, to facilitate the participation of people in political, economic, social and cultural life, as a fundamental right. Nevertheless, the Constitution guarantees the right to access information which, along with the right to interact with public authorities, create the first steps to empowering citizens to participation in decision-making.

In general terms, the right to information is further elaborated by the Law on the Right to Information,³⁴ the rulings of which are designated to ensure public access to information. The law also aims at encouraging integrity, transparency and accountability of the public sector bodies. However, it was the 2014 Law on Notification and Public Consultation³⁵ that provides the framework for citizen participation in policy-making in Albania. This law regulates the process of notification and public consultation of the draft laws, national and local strategic draft documents, and policies of high interest to the public. It stipulates the procedural rules which shall be applied in order to ensure public transparency and participation in the policy-making and decision-making processes of public entities.

Specifically, citizens' right to participate in local government decision-making is strongly embedded in the organic law regulating local governance in Albania,³⁶ as a form of real decentralization of power from higher levels of government to local communities. This law devotes an entire chapter to rules on transparency, consultation and civic participation. It prescribes that promoting an all-inclusive participation of the community in local governance is one of the fundamental missions of local self-government units in Albania. According to the

³⁴ Law no 119/2014 on the Right to Information.

³⁵ Law no 146/2014 on Notification and Public Consultation.

³⁶ Law no 139/2015 on Local Self-Government.

law, local self-governments shall guarantee transparency of their activity to the public and are obliged to guarantee public participation in the process of decision-making. The municipal council meetings are open to the public and every citizen shall be allowed to attend them as stipulated in the statutes of the municipal council. This law specifically provides that before considering and approving acts, municipal or regional councils shall hold consultation sessions with the community, and in the case of municipal budgets, municipal fiscal policy and a few other major local government rights and responsibilities, such as the adoption of local development strategies, rulings on territorial management, rulings affecting the entire community etc., the consultation sessions with the community are mandatory. Furthermore, each community has the right to present citizens' initiatives on matters within the jurisdiction of the local self-government unit to the municipal council for decision.

The Albanian Constitution foresees also local referenda as one of the main forms of local democracy and direct exercise of people's sovereignty and as a key form of local self-government (Article 108). The initiative for a local referendum on a local government issue can be exercised by: (i) 10 per cent of the voters registered in the electoral registers of the respective local unit or 20,000 of them, whichever is smaller; (ii) a number of municipal councils, representing not less than one third of the population of a county, which have the right to request the holding of a referendum on a local government issue at the county level. However, a legal framework to allow the implementation of local referenda has been missing since the adoption of the Constitution in 1998, and in fact, there are no cases of local referenda in Albania. It is difficult to explain the reasons why Albanian policymakers have not adopted the implementing framework for local referenda over the past two decades. The strong legacy of centralistic institutions and political divisions at national and local level certainly plays an important role, along with the interplay of other social and political factors, such as trust in government and institutions, including on local referenda.

Albania enjoys a sound legal framework that would ensure local government transparency and facilitate citizens participation in local decision-making. However, there is a substantial gap between the provisions of the laws and their actual implementation. While the practice of inviting citizens to participate in consultations, discussions, presentations and roundtables to inform citizens on local government plans and strategies has been increasing, still implementation of real participation in decision making remains challenging.³⁷ Citizens are not fully aware of the existence of mechanisms ensuring their participation and there is a lot of skepticism about the concrete impact of their involvement in decision-making.³⁸ This skepticism is rooted also in the fact that in most cases, citizens are presented a completed or almost completed proposal before its final approval. This setting does not allow citizens to be involved in the early stages of decision-making, which would contribute to building trust in their government and participating in the development of their own community. Monitoring

³⁷ Congress of Local and Regional Authorities and Partners Albania for Change and Development, 'Handbook on Transparency and Citizen Participation in Albania' (Council of Europe 2020).

³⁸ IDRA Research, 'Citizen Participation in Decision-Making in Albania' (IDRA 2017).

of local government activity with a view to holding them accountable is mostly driven on a project basis by NGOs. Some municipalities have adopted open government initiatives to facilitate both monitoring and accountability. However, actions by individuals or organizations on such open data portals are rather rare, except for investigative journalists.

Overall, the majority of Albanian citizens perceives the central and local government as not transparent or accountable and between 2016 and 2019, the perceived decline in transparency is six percentage points for the central government and seven percentage points for local government.³⁹ According to the 2019 assessment of the Institute for Democracy and Mediation, at the local level 24.6 per cent of respondents participated in a public consultation meeting, with the main reason for this low turnout being the lack of trust in such processes. The report finds out also that at least six in ten respondents believe that local public hearings are formal events with limited influence on municipal decisions and that suggestions coming from civil society and interest groups on draft laws are not taken into consideration. Another survey found out that between 2016 and 2019 there is an improvement regarding the institutional framework for participation and citizen engagement, but there is a decrease in the involvement of all stakeholders in decision-making.⁴⁰ Additionally, 70.6 per cent of respondents reported that they do not have sufficient opportunities to participate in decision-making at the central level. At the local level, respondents were slightly more optimistic about opportunities to participate. 58.6 per cent reported that they do not have sufficient opportunity, meaning that according to 41.4 per cent of the respondents there is sufficient opportunity to participate in local decision-making processes.⁴¹ The assessment surveys show no major differences with regard to citizens' interest or perception of opportunities to participate in decision-making at the central and local level according to urban or rural residency.⁴²

In short, despite significant progress, in particular in the institutional framework and mechanisms, Albanian civil society is still struggling to increase influence on governance at both national and local level and to ensure sustainable impact. However, it must be acknowledged that there are many local governments who take a proactive approach in involving citizens in their decision-making processes, both in urban and rural areas.⁴³

³⁹ IDM – Institute for Democracy and Mediation, 'Survey Report: Opinion Poll – Trust in Governance in Albania' (IDM 2019).

⁴⁰ IDRA Research and Human Development Promotion Center, 'Local Governance Mapping in Albania' (2020).

⁴¹ *ibid.*

⁴² *ibid.*

⁴³ See, for example, report section 6.1. on Civic Engagement towards Urban-Rural Linkages in Albania.

References to Scientific and Non-Scientific Publications

Legal Documents:

Law no 119/2014 on the Right to Information

Law no 146/2014 on Notification and Public Consultation

Law no 139/2015 on Local Self-Government

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Congress of Local and Regional Authorities and Partners Albania for Change and Development, 'Handbook on Transparency and Citizen Participation in Albania' (Council of Europe 2020)

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This project has received funding from
the European Union's Horizon 2020 re-
search and innovation programme under
grant agreement No 823961.

